

Systematic Survey for Otter Activity on Nantucket April 2014

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Abstract

Though river otters are common throughout Massachusetts, they were not documented on Nantucket until 2008 when tracks were photographed by biologist Edie Ray and verified by the state furbearer biologist. To follow up on these verified tracks staff from Nantucket Conservation Foundation and BiodiversityWorks conducted a systematic survey of suitable river otter habitat on Nantucket with the goal of documenting whether river otters had colonized the island. A total of 26 sites were surveyed for otter activity on April 2nd, 2014. We spent ~16 biologist hours surveying these sites and did not locate any otter sign (latrines, scat, tracks, and trails). However, there was ample fresh and brackish ponds, with cover habitat for dens, to support an otter population should they become established.

Introduction

The river otter (*Lontra canadensis*) is widely distributed across North America, from Florida to Alaska. This large mustelid occupied every major waterway of the United States and Canada until at least the nineteenth century. By 1977, however, they occupied < 75% of their historic range due to draining of wetlands, overharvesting for fur, and pollution. Wetland conservation and restoration in the 1980s, and reintroduction programs in some states in the 1990's, successfully restored river otters to almost 90% of their historic range by 1998. The seminal research on river otter biology and behavioral ecology was in the lakes and rivers of the western United States. Since then, much of the research and monitoring occurred in areas where the species was extirpated and reintroduced. Alaska is one exception; the Exxon Valdez oil spill in 1989 triggered studies aimed at assessing the condition and recovery of river otters affected by the spill (Bowyer et al. 2003). The Valdez study was the first to focus on coastal river otters, and

documented that coastal otters are more gregarious due to an abundance of prey in estuarine and coastal habitats. In Massachusetts, river otters were always common due to the abundance of freshwater and coastline that provide excellent resources for the species and opportunity for dispersal or colonization across state lines. Very few scientists have studied river otter in Massachusetts. Abundance and distribution information comes from trapping records and local observations, but pelt harvest has declined since 1996 when a statewide ban on body gripping traps limited trapping success and reduced the number of fur trappers active in Massachusetts. With reduced trapping effort, river otter populations are likely increasing throughout the Commonwealth.

River otters are a top predator in our watersheds and act as a sentinel species for humans and other organisms that depend on healthy ponds and waterways for food and habitat. Without any baseline data on otter activity and distribution, it would be difficult to quantify any population-level changes over time and thus infer the ecological health of our watersheds. Therefore, gathering baseline information on river otter distribution, habitat use, activity patterns, and diet will allow us to detect changes in the population as well as our watersheds, allowing us to be proactive in avoiding drastic declines in the species or the water quality.

Increasing impairment of Martha's Vineyard watersheds prompted BiodiversityWorks to begin gathering baseline information on river otters on the island. In 2009, we began surveying the island's ponds, beaches and wetlands for otter activity. Though river otters are active at night and can be fairly elusive they are quite comfortable on land and habitually use the same "haul-out" or "latrine" areas within their home range. Otters roll in these areas to dry and clean their fur and leave scent mounds (mounds of grass/vegetation) and scat to communicate with other otters. Scent marking in river otters is not a territorial behavior, it is used to communicate information about group members, reproductive status, and hierarchy and aids in mutual avoidance (Blundell et al. 2002; Rostain et al. 2004; Ben-David et al. 2005; Oldham and Black 2009). Locating and monitoring these latrine sites is an effective, non-invasive method in learning about river otter distribution, habitat use, activity patterns, and diet (Gallant et al. 2007). Placing trail cameras at latrine sites can give further information about activity patterns as well as behavior, and group

sizes (Olson et. al 2008; Stevens and Serfass 2008; Baldwin 2013).

During our survey of otter activity on the Vineyard, from 2009-2011, we documented over 150 latrine sites and 6 dens. We also identified several overland routes and continue to map these trails that connect latrine sites during the winter. Active latrine sites located during the initial survey were monitored once per month to document activity patterns and collect scat for diet analysis. Over 200 scat samples were collected and processed. This data was used to develop a “Guide to River Otter Diet Analysis for SE Massachusetts”. The first version was completed in 2011, by Luanne Johnson. In 2013, Liz Baldwin completed her master’s thesis on “Activity patterns, behaviors, and population status of the North American river otter (*Lontra canadensis*) in a northeast coastal environment, Martha’s Vineyard, Massachusetts” using trail cameras to collect her data. We also mapped river otter activity on Naushon Island, and completed some preliminary surveys in Woods Hole/Falmouth area.

Collecting this baseline information on river otters on the Vineyard has given us an understanding of how they utilize these coastal environments. After founding BiodiversityWorks (BWorks) in 2011, we are now in a position to begin expanding the project to gather more baseline information about river otters in this region. Citizen reports from Cape Cod indicate river otters are common, but no maps exist showing abundance or distribution. In 2008, biologist Edie Ray photographed the first river otter tracks on Nantucket near Madequecham, which were verified by the state furbearer biologist. Our goal was to conduct a systematic survey of Nantucket to document presence/absence of river otter (latrines, trails, and sign) in suitable habitat and determine if river otter had colonized the island.

Methods

The first phase of this project was to bring staff from Nantucket Conservation Foundation (NCF) to Martha’s Vineyard to visit otter latrine sites and learn how to identify otter sign in this similar coastal environment. Karen C. Beattie and Danielle O’Dell from NCF came to the Vineyard on March 19, 2014 and visited 7 latrine sites in varying habitats. We were able to see scat, trails, scent mounds, tracks and one den. This gave NCF staff a good sense of the habitat river otters utilize in these coastal environments.

The next phase was to survey Nantucket for otter activity in suitable habitat. We identified 33 suitable habitat sites on Nantucket using river otter latrine site characteristics from Martha's Vineyard (Map 1). Some examples of suitable habitat include fresh water ponds near the ocean, the heads of brackish ponds where the water is fresher, grassy areas between two fresh ponds, and docks that extend out into fresh water ponds. Due to time constraints Muskeget and Tuckernuck Island and Great Point area were not surveyed. They should be surveyed in the future as they have suitable habitat and are geographically positioned closer to the Vineyard (Muskeget and Tuckernuck) and Monomoy (Great Point) making it the first place otters would likely land if making that ocean crossing.

After BWorks identified suitable otter habitat on Nantucket via Google™ Earth maps NCF then used their local knowledge to identify sites that either were not accessible due to time constraints, private ownership, or were not as suitable as they appeared on Google Earth. We settled on 17 pond/wetland/coastal areas to survey. On April 2, 2014, BWorks biologists traveled to Nantucket to survey these sites with NCF biologists.

Recent studies have shown that river otter activity at latrine sites are highest during March/April (Olson et. al 2008; Stevens and Serfass 2008; Baldwin 2013). This is a time when young of the previous year are dispersing and the breeding season is at its peak. Therefore, if there are resident otters on Nantucket we believed March/April surveys would provide the best opportunity to detect them. During the survey we split into two teams and surveyed a total of 29 sites (Map 2A and B). At each site we recorded habitat characteristics, GPS coordinates and otter activity, if any. We also took photos of the habitat at each site. Photos and survey site locations were given to NCF for their files and future reference.

Results

A total of 29 sites (~17 pond/wetland/coastal areas) were surveyed for otter activity on Nantucket (Table 1). We spent ~16 biologists' hours surveying the sites, but we did not detect any otter scat, tracks, or scent mounds at any of them. Approximately 11 of the sites visited were identified as prime suitable habitat and would have otter activity if otters were present on the island.

Discussion

It is not surprising that we did not detect an established population of river otters on Nantucket, as open ocean is considered a barrier to river otter dispersal (Kruuk 2006). However, the tracks found in 2008 suggest it is possible for otters to find their way to Nantucket. Otters are found on the North shore of the Vineyard and on the Elizabeth islands but it is unknown if otters move between the islands. Future genetic testing of populations on both islands could possibly answer this question. We did not survey Musket Island, Tuckernuck Island, or Great Point on Nantucket, which all have suitable habitat. It is possible otters are active in one or more of these sites, but coastal river otter home ranges are typically 8-45 km of shoreline, so we believe they would also be active in the areas we surveyed if they occupied these other sites. These other sites should be surveyed in the future to determine presence/absence of river otter. If river otters had colonized Nantucket, we are certain our comprehensive survey of suitable habitat, by experienced biologists, would have detected their presence. During a yearlong survey of 25 active river otter latrines on the Vineyard, BWorks staff noted that otter scat takes several months to degrade completely. Thus, even a low-density otter population would leave enough scat in multiple sites for confirmation of presence/absence in a one-day survey. In addition, April is a time when river otters are moving across the landscape and increasing their scenting activity at latrine sites. Therefore, if they were present on Nantucket, the probability of detection was high.

Nantucket has many fresh ponds, both inland and near the ocean, that are suitable habitat for river otters. The amount of food available in these ponds however, is unknown. Biologists on Nantucket have reported that the osprey population has had poor productivity in the last few years. There is speculation that it is related to a decline in food resources. If food resources are limited in these ponds it may reduce the number of otters that could colonize the area. Otters however, will feed in the ocean nearshore and are opportunistic feeders. Therefore, we believe there are ample resources to support an otter population. Overall, Nantucket has fewer freshwater habitats than the Vineyard, which will limit the size of any river otter population that may colonize in the future. Little is known about the level of food availability on both islands and would be a valuable study for the future.

Conclusion

This systematic survey of suitable river otter habitat provided baseline data documenting river otter absence on the Island. In 5-10 years, or if river otter sightings are reported on Nantucket, NCF staff could repeat this standardized survey to document presence/absence at the same 29 sites we surveyed using the knowledge they gained from visiting otter latrine sites, trails and dens on the Vineyard. BiodiversityWorks will continue to work with NCF to identify any otter sign discovered on Nantucket in the future. While we did not document river otter presence on Nantucket during this survey, we believe otters are capable of colonizing through dispersal from Monomoy or Chappaquiddick, which have robust otter populations.

Literature Cited

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Tables and Figures

Map 1: Map of areas identified as suitable habitat for river otter latrines based on knowledge of the species habitats on Martha's Vineyard.

Map 2A: Sites surveyed for river otter presence/absence on Nantucket, April 2nd 2014

Map 2B: Sites surveyed for river otter activity on Nantucket, April 2nd 2014

Table 1: Summary of data collected during the systematic survey for otter activity on Nantucket, April 2nd, 2014. Summary includes date of survey, site name, description, GPS coordinates, and otter activity presence/absence (Y/N). Photos of sites visited during the survey were sent in a separate file to NCF, below is the name of the photo associated with the site.

Date Surveyed	Site Name	Site description	Lat	Long	Otter Activity	Photo Name	Notes
4/2/2014	Capaum Pond	Fresh pond with phragmites, shrub and cattail border. Pond near ocean. Nice footpath on outer edge	41.291644	-70.139453	N	None	
4/2/2014	Clark's Cove West	Cattails, shrubs, phragmites and meadows	41.26457	-70.16129	N	Clark_Cove_2	
4/2/2014	Clark's Cove. W. Branch Hummock	Pond and ocean meet	41.25809	-70.17002	N	clark_cove_beach	
4/2/2014	Clark's Cove. West side of W. Branch	Heathland trail from pond to soft grass	41.25912	-70.16895	N	Clark_cove_1	
4/2/2014	Clark's Cove; Head	Head of cove with trail from it. Cattails, shrubs to grassy field	41.26293	-70.16713	N	Clark_cove_head	
4/2/2014	Columbus and Midland Road	Head of pond to meadow	41.27139	-70.19131	N	None	
Nov. 2013	Field Station	Fresh Pond	NA	NA	N	None	Liz checked grassy areas during NBI conference no activity seen

Date Surveyed	Site Name	Site description	Lat	Long	Otter Activity	Photo Name	Notes
4/2/2014	Hither Creek	brackish marsh and salt marsh	41.27969	-70.18736	N	Hither_Creek	
4/2/2014	Hummock Pond beach side	Pond near beach, grassy	41.25674	-70.16442	N	Hummock_Pond_beach	
4/2/2014	Hummock Pond North end	3 fresh ponds. Checked the heads, grassy habitat and shrubs.	41.28067	-70.13572	N	Hummock_N_1/2	good habitat
4/2/2014	Hummock Pond W. East side Ram Pasture	Head of cove, shrubs, grassland	41.25938	-70.16176	N	Hummock_Pond_W	
4/2/2014	Long Pond Massasoit Bridge	Grassy edge of pond with trail to grassy footpath	41.27269	-70.18425	N	Long_pond_bridge	
4/2/2014	Long Pond North end	Brackish pond grassy and phragmites borders it. Dock and cattails	41.28389	-70.17018	N	Long_Pond_N_1/2/3	
4/2/2014	Long Pond South	Brackish pond, dock at pond edge	41.26954	-70.19375	N	Long_Pond_S_1/2	good habitat
4/2/2014	Long Pond, W. side, 2nd bridge	Brackish pond cattails, phragmites and shrubs	41.28148	-70.17604	N	Long_Pond_W_1/2	
4/2/2014	Madequecham	Phragmites patch, fresh water. Shallow during survey. Near where tracks were seen in 2008	41.243278	-70.04512	N	Madequecham	Marginal habitat
4/2/2014	Madequecham	Where tracks were seen in 2008	41.24292	-70.0437	N	None	

Date Surveyed	Site Name	Site description	Lat	Long	Otter Activity	Photo Name	Notes
4/2/2014	Medovie Creek	Salt Pond, salt marsh. Docks in pond in summer check for scat then.	41.30655	-70.01418	N	Medovie_Creek_1/2	Marginal habitat
4/2/2014	Miacomet Pond	Fresh pond. Surveyed Land Bank property. Edge of pond overgrown brush not great habitat	41.258204	-70.106592	N	None	Check head of this pond in future grassy area (someone's yard)
4/2/2014	Miacomet Pond	Where pond meets ocean	41.24348	-70.11843	N	Miacomet_1/2/3	good habitat
4/2/2014	Miacomet Pond	West side off trail. Cove, culvert with grassy area dividing two bodies of water	41.255052	-70.112635	N	Miacomet_W_1/2	good habitat
4/2/2014	Millies Bridge opposite Hither Creek	Entrance to Hither Creek and bridge. Lots of grass and otter habitat	41.27218	-70.203355	N	Millies_Bridge	good place for an otter trail to other pond
4/2/2014	Ram Pasture South	Grassy road between wetlands	41.26302	-70.15337	N	Ram_Pasture_S	
4/2/2014	Sesachacha Pond beach side	Near pond opening. Ocean meets pond.	41.30086	-69.9755	N	Sesachacha_Pond_beach	Okay habitat. Head of pond is better
4/2/2014	Sesachacha Pond Road side	Great Pond, brackish, open 2x a year. Head of pond.	41.29029	-69.98409	N	Sesachacha_Pond_1/2	good habitat

Date Surveyed	Site Name	Site description	Lat	Long	Otter Activity	Photo Name	Notes
4/2/2014	Squam Pond	Fresh pond close to ocean. Good grassy areas near pond	41.31543	-69.98715	N	Squam_Pond_1/2	good habitat
4/2/2014	Tom Never's Pond	Fresh pond near ocean, shallow. Flooded at time of survey	41.24599	-69.98637	N	Never Pond_1/2	good habitat
3/28/2014	Tom Never's Pond West side	NA	NA	NA	N	None	surveyed by Danielle prior
4/2/2014	Washing and Maxey Pond	Kettle hole pond surrounded by shrubs. Grassy path from pond to road towards Capaum pond	41.28721	-70.13389	N	Washing_Maxey_1	good habitat
4/2/2014	Washing and Maxey Pond	Mowed path thru shrubs, woody debris substrate. Grassy path along NE side	41.28569	-70.1352	N	Washing_Maxey_2	
4/2/2014	Weeweeder	Fresh ponds with road in-between. Pond had fish. Pine needle, grassy areas around pond.	41.24674	-70.10114	N	Weeweeder_1/2	good habitat

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